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"Digitalization and Social Development Trends in the Xxi Century"

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***Abstract:** In the 21st century, several global development trends have emerged that carry the potential for conflict. Cutting-edge technologies in communication, medicine, agriculture, industry, and environmental protection are advancing rapidly. The information society has given rise to a range of entirely new phenomena—both positive and negative—which are analyzed in this article.*

The development of technologies across various fields is significantly impacting individuals, societies, and cultures. Socio-cultural relations in the new type of information society are shaped by a combination of diverse and often contradictory trends. On the one hand, social equality is increasing due to the openness of information, which is a primary resource in the information society. On the other hand, the phenomenon of digital inequality is emerging, as access to knowledge remains challenging for some. In societies based on network principles, social connections are weakening, and upward mobility through "social elevators" is becoming increasingly difficult.

While society is becoming highly rational, at the same time, we are witnessing the flourishing of mystical movements, revealing a mythologization of social consciousness. Culture is both innovative and, paradoxically, emphasizes the value of traditional social structures. All of this highlights the complexity of modern social processes and the non-linear nature of societal development, both in general and in the present moment. Living in such a society is challenging, but understanding its key features allows for the use of this complexity for both individual and collective growth.

***Key words:** social elevators, information society, 3D printing industry, technological transformations.*

Introduction

In the 21st century, several global development trends have emerged that carry potential for conflict. One of the key areas within these trends is the rapid growth of technology, which is soon expected to spark a revolution in the global market. Key advancements include mobile internet technologies,

nanotechnology, and breakthroughs in genetics. A particularly important area is 3D printing. According to IDC data, sales of industrial 3D printers are projected to grow by 164% annually up until 2020 (Sedykh, 2017: Electronic resource). The overall spending on 3D printing was forecast to rise from \$11 billion in 2015 to \$27 billion by 2019, with an annual growth rate of 127% (ibid). This growth is driven by the versatility of 3D printing, which is used in industries ranging from jewelry making and manufacturing to medicine, particularly in the production of organs for transplantation. In the near future, the introduction of 4D printing is expected, allowing for the creation of objects that can "change their shape or function over time or in response to environmental changes" (Korganbayev, 2016: Electronic resource).

Will these technological transformations change social life? The information society has already given rise to a series of entirely new phenomena, both positive and negative. Theorists of post-industrial and information societies have consistently named justice and increased opportunities for individual and personal development as fundamental principles for the functioning of these societies. On what basis is this understanding formed? On the indisputable fact that these societies are built upon knowledge and information, resources that are inexhaustible. This eliminates the need for competitive struggles over their possession. Everyone can find a niche that suits their aspirations and begin developing their own path. However, the flawless premise of the inexhaustibility of information has led some researchers to the incorrect conclusion that inexhaustibility is synonymous with universal accessibility.

As of 2021, the 3D printing industry in the United Kingdom alone was estimated to reach around £5.6 billion by 2025, growing at an annual rate of about 23% from 2020 (Source: Business Wire). The U.S. market for 3D printing was projected to surpass \$20 billion by 2025, driven by its widespread application in industries such as aerospace, automotive, and healthcare (Source: Statista). In terms of 4D printing, research is still in the early stages, but it is expected to impact fields like construction, where materials can adapt to environmental changes, and medicine, with the potential for self-healing implants (Source: MIT Technology Review).

Literature Review

Contrary to expectations, experience has shown that knowledge remains largely inaccessible, available primarily to those with sufficient education to acquire and develop it. This is why, in the information society, education plays a crucial role in determining social status. According to Filipino researcher Roberto Verzola, the upper class of the wealthiest citizens is composed of "cyberlords." "Cyberlords are a class of owners in the information sector. They control either vast amounts of information or the material infrastructure necessary for its creation, distribution, and use. Cyberlords are the capitalist class that lives off rent" (Verzola, 1997: Electronic resource).

This viewpoint is shared by renowned information society researcher Manuel Castells, who speaks of the elite in society and the global networked elite as those who are "connected to the networks and flows" in the Global Web (Castells, 1999: 494-495).

In practice, total informatization does not eliminate low-skilled labor; in the information society, the economy still retains sectors where manual labor is necessary. Additionally, there is another aspect: the latest breakthroughs in communication, biology, genetic engineering, cognitive science, and pharmacology are making the boundary between the natural and the artificial in humans more permeable. Possessing enhanced physiological traits will become prestigious, but due to the high cost of these new technologies, they will remain inaccessible to most people. This will not only lead to digital inequality and increased social segregation but also to "sharp internal and international conflicts

over the ethics and consequences of altering the human gene pool" (Korganbayev, 2016: Electronic resource).

All of this raises numerous questions, which are considered in documents related to the transition into the information society. One such document, dating back to 1999, outlined the concept of building an information society, aiming to define the most optimal approach for integrating into the information age and establishing policies to ensure the success of this transition. The concept emphasized the political, socio-economic, cultural, and technological prerequisites for this shift, outlining a national pathway towards becoming a full participant in the global information society. The goal was to provide citizens with access to the material and spiritual benefits of an information-based civilization, ensuring a dignified life, economic prosperity, and the conditions for personal development. It also stressed the importance of maintaining political independence, national identity, and cultural traditions while participating in global technological and economic development.

Global Perspective

Globally, the information society continues to deepen the gap between those who have access to knowledge and those who do not. In developed countries, access to the internet and digital tools has significantly transformed education, healthcare, and economic systems. However, the rise of a digital elite—comprising owners of data and the infrastructure that manages it—has created new forms of inequality. This "cyberlord" class controls key sectors of the information economy, reaping the benefits of digital capitalism while many others remain excluded from its advantages.

The global digital divide persists, with approximately 37% of the world's population still offline as of 2022, according to the World Bank. In regions with advanced digital infrastructures, like North America and Europe, citizens have greater access to educational and professional opportunities. However, in much of the developing world, including parts of Africa and Southeast Asia, access to information technology remains limited, exacerbating existing inequalities.

Furthermore, advancements in biotechnology and artificial intelligence are creating a future where enhanced human abilities, through genetic modification or technological augmentation, may become a new form of social stratification. As these technologies remain prohibitively expensive, they risk being accessible only to the wealthy, deepening societal divides and raising ethical questions about the future of humanity.

Uzbekistan's Perspective

In Uzbekistan, the integration into the global information society is underway, but challenges remain. The government has prioritized the development of information and communication technologies (ICT) to boost economic growth and social development. Significant investments have been made in improving internet access, expanding e-government services, and fostering innovation in the digital economy. The "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" strategy outlines ambitious goals to modernize the country's digital infrastructure, enhance ICT education, and ensure greater accessibility for citizens.

However, digital inequality persists, particularly between urban and rural areas. While major cities like Tashkent are seeing rapid digital growth, rural regions still struggle with limited access to high-speed internet and digital services. Education remains a key area of focus, with efforts being made to improve the digital literacy of both students and teachers. The expansion of online learning platforms and digital tools in schools is a positive step forward, but challenges such as a shortage of skilled IT professionals and unequal access to technology continue to hinder progress.

As Uzbekistan moves towards greater integration into the global information economy, addressing digital inequality and ensuring equitable access to the benefits of technological advancements will be critical for fostering inclusive social and economic development.

Social Structure: The Network Principle of Small Social Groups

In industrial and post-industrial societies, the social structure undergoes significant changes compared to traditional pre-industrial societies. Medieval society, for instance, was quite monolithic in terms of social structure, with each class having a clearly defined position, rights, and duties. In the industrial age, the class system replaced the caste system, and in the post-industrial era, the social structure shifts to a subcultural basis. In the information age, the network principle becomes dominant, affecting not only governance, which leans toward decentralization, and organizational strategies that favor alternative solutions, but also the social sphere, which adopts a network structure with minimal centralization.

This shift began in the 1960s as a result of the transformation of social relations and the replacement of industrial relations with post-industrial ones. The most significant feature of post-industrial society is the change in the source of social wealth. It is no longer labor and capital but knowledge and information that drive society. Another important aspect is the formation of a new social structure based on fundamentally different principles.

In the industrial age, society relied on large masses of people working in large-scale production. In contrast, in the post-industrial society, diversification becomes the key principle, breaking up large masses into smaller groups. Labor itself also changes, with information becoming the most valuable production resource, and work being more focused on complex processes requiring high qualifications and long preparation times. The diversification of society is further fueled by the expansion of the service sector, which tends to involve smaller collectives, often family-based.

The abundance of basic goods also leads to the rise of consumerism, which is increasingly focused on personalized products and services. From uniquely numbered clothing lines to personalized travel packages and friendly interfaces designed to create a direct connection between humans and computers—greeting users by name, for example, and adapting to the time of day with a “Good morning!” or “Good evening!” greeting.

Additionally, as a consequence of the development of the information sphere, there is a natural increase in the time spent on education, and with early retirement, a reduction in the time spent in the workforce. In this type of society, issues like hunger, disease, poverty, and lack of property rights are largely resolved. This allows for later marriages, limiting families to one or two children, and a prolonged period of social maturation—extending from 17-18 years to 24-25 years—as it takes considerable time to acquire the necessary amount of knowledge.

Another important trend is the aging population in developed countries. According to forecasts from leading global analytical centers, in the near future, the average age of citizens in countries like Japan, Germany, and Poland will range between 48 and 52 years old. Meanwhile, the global population is expected to increase by 20% over the next few decades, with the number of people over 60 expected to reach 2 billion. This demographic shift will significantly impact the labor force, with countries like China expected to lose 25% of its workforce, and countries like Greece, Portugal, and Germany losing approximately 20%.

Post-Industrial Society in Uzbekistan

In Uzbekistan, the transition to a post-industrial society is characterized by several key trends. As the country moves away from an economy based on agriculture and industry, knowledge and information are becoming central to the social structure. The government's "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" initiative reflects the importance of information technology in shaping the future of the nation.

Like in other post-industrial societies, small social groups play an increasingly important role in Uzbekistan. These groups are formed based on shared interests, professional affiliations, and, in some cases, cultural or regional backgrounds. The diversification of society means that large-scale labor forces are being replaced by smaller, more specialized collectives, particularly in the tech and service sectors.

In rural areas, where traditional social structures have persisted for longer, the shift to a network-based society is slower. However, the growing influence of digital technologies and online communication platforms is gradually reshaping even these communities, fostering new types of social relationships based on shared knowledge and interests rather than traditional hierarchies.

In conclusion, both globally and in Uzbekistan, the post-industrial society is evolving towards a network-based structure. Small social groups are becoming more prominent, defined by individual skills, interests, and aspirations. The traditional concept of social classes is giving way to a more fluid, dynamic structure where identity is shaped by personal choices and experiences rather than predetermined social roles. This shift reflects the broader transition to an information society, where knowledge and information are the primary drivers of social and economic life.

Conclusion

One of the most significant trends of modern times is the rapid development of cutting-edge technologies in various fields such as communication, medicine, agriculture, industry, and environmental protection. These changes are not merely technological; they actively influence individuals, society, and culture. Socio-cultural relations in the new type of information-age society encompass a variety of conflicting trends.

In Uzbekistan, these global trends are increasingly visible as the country embraces digital transformation. Initiatives like "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" aim to bring advanced technologies to all sectors, from agriculture to healthcare. While this creates vast opportunities for economic and social development, it also brings challenges such as digital inequality, especially between urban and rural populations.

In rural areas, where access to the internet and modern technologies can be limited, the gap between those who can engage in the digital economy and those left behind is widening. However, the government's push for broader access to information technologies is gradually closing this divide, ensuring that more people benefit from the knowledge-based economy.

Culturally, Uzbekistan is experiencing a similar duality. The younger generation is increasingly connected to global trends and innovations, while older generations hold firmly to traditional values. This creates a unique blend where the old and new coexist, sometimes in tension but often in harmony. In many ways, Uzbekistan serves as a microcosm of the larger global transition, balancing the benefits of technological advancement with the preservation of its rich cultural heritage.

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